

**Perinatal outcome of pregnancy complicated by twin anemia–polycythemia sequence:
systematic review and meta-analysis**

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Contribution

What are the novel findings of this work?

Spontaneous TAPS may have a better prognosis than post-Laser TAPS. No substantial difference was noticed in terms of perinatal mortality and morbidity between the group of TAPS managed expectantly and the groups treated by laser, intrauterine transfusion or selective reduction.

What are the clinical implications of this work?

The present meta-analysis provides pooled estimates of the risks of perinatal mortality and morbidity and preterm birth in twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS, stratified by the type of TAPS and different management options.

ABSTRACT

Objective: To report the perinatal outcome of monochorionic diamniotic (MCDA) twin pregnancy complicated by twin anemia polycythemia sequence (TAPS), according to the type of TAPS (spontaneous or post-laser) and the management option adopted.

Methods: Medline, Embase and Cochrane Library databases were searched for studies reporting on the outcome of twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS. Inclusion criteria were non-anomalous MCDA twin pregnancies with a diagnosis of TAPS. The primary outcome was perinatal mortality; the secondary outcomes were neonatal morbidity and preterm birth (PTB). The outcomes were stratified according to the type of TAPS (spontaneous or following laser treatment for TTTS) and the management option adopted (expectant, laser, intra-uterine transfusion [IUT] or selective reduction [SR]). Random effects meta-analyses of proportions were used to analyze the data.

Results:

Perinatal outcome was assessed according to whether TAPS occurred spontaneously or post-laser in 506 pregnancies (38 studies). IUD occurred in 5.2% (95% CI, 3.6–7.1) of twins with spontaneous TAPS and in 10.2% (95% CI, 7.4-13.3) of those with post-laser TAPS, while the corresponding rates of NND were 4.0% (95% CI, 2.6-5.7) and 9.2% (95% CI, 6.6-12.3), respectively. Severe neonatal morbidity occurred in 29.3% (95% CI, 25.6-33.1) of twins after spontaneous TAPS and in 33.3% (95% CI, 17.4-51.8) after post-laser TAPS, while the corresponding rates of severe neurological morbidity were 4.0% (95% CI, 3.5-5.7) and 11.1% (95% CI, 6.2-17.2), respectively. PTB complicated 86.3% (95% CI, 77.2- 93.3) of pregnancies with spontaneous TAPS and all cases with post-laser TAPS (100%; 95% CI, 84.3-100). Iatrogenic PTB was more frequent than spontaneous PTB in both groups. Perinatal outcome was assessed according to the different management options in 418 pregnancies (21 studies). IUD occurred in 9.8% (95% CI, 4.3-17.1) of twins managed expectantly and in 13.1% (95% CI, 9.2-17.6), 12.1% (95% CI, 7.7-17.3) and 7.6% (95% CI, 1.3-18.5) of those treated with laser, IUT and SR, respectively. Severe neonatal morbidity affected 27.3% (95% CI, 13.6-43.6) of twins in the expectant management group, 28.7% (95% CI, 22.7-35.1) of those in the laser surgery group, 38.2% (95% CI 18.3-60.5) of those in the IUT group and 23.3% (95% CI 10.5-39.2) of those in the SR group. PTB complicated 80.4% (95% CI, 59.8-94.8), 73.4% (95% CI, 48.1- 92.3), 100% (95% CI, 76.5- 100) and 100% (95% CI, 39.8-100) of pregnancies after expectant management, laser, IUT and SR, respectively.

Conclusions: The present meta-analysis provides pooled estimates of the risks of perinatal mortality, neonatal morbidity and preterm birth in twin pregnancy complicated by TAPS, stratified by the type of TAPS and different management options. Although a direct comparison could not be performed, the results from this systematic review suggest that spontaneous TAPS may have a better prognosis than post-Laser TAPS. No differences in terms of mortality and morbidity were observed when comparing different management options for TAPS, although these findings should be interpreted with caution in view of the limitations of the included studies. Individualized prenatal management, taking into account the severity of TAPS and gestational age, is currently the recommended strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Monochorionic diamniotic (MCDA) twin pregnancies are at higher risk of perinatal mortality and morbidity compared with dichorionic twin pregnancies, which is mainly the consequence of twin to twin transfusion syndrome (TTTS), selective FGR and Twin anemia polycythemia sequence (TAPS). TAPS is a complication of monochorionic twin pregnancies that occurs when small placental anastomoses (<1 mm) lead to chronic and slow inter-twin transfusion without volume disparity of amniotic fluid between the donor twin and the recipient twin¹. While significantly discordant hemoglobin levels and reticulocyte counts between the twins comprise the postnatal diagnostic criteria of TAPS, prenatal diagnosis of TAPS is based on the presence of Doppler ultrasound abnormalities without signs of polyhydramnios in the recipient or oligohydramnios in the donor. In TAPS, fetal middle cerebral artery peak systolic velocity (MCA-PSV) is increased in the donor twin (>1.5 Multiples of the Median [MoM]), suggesting fetal anemia, while it is decreased (<1.0 MoM) in the recipient twin, consistent with polycythemia²⁻⁴. The antenatal staging system of TAPS, which can be useful to guide intervention, includes different degrees of fetal hemodynamic impairment assessed by Doppler studies, with demise of one or both fetuses representing the final stage^{2, 5}.

TAPS may occur spontaneously in 3-5% of monochorionic twin pregnancies and after laser surgery for twin-to twin transfusion syndrome (TTTS) in 2-16%, due to residual anastomoses⁶⁻⁸. Indeed, the equatorial dichorionization that is performed during the Solomon technique, which reduces the risk of residual anastomoses, is associated with a 5-fold reduction in the rate of post-Laser TAPS, as compared to the selective technique^{9, 10}. The knowledge of TAPS pathogenesis has improved through the use of color dye injection of the placenta¹¹. Conversely, there is scarce evidence about its natural history or perinatal outcome. Furthermore, the optimal antenatal management approach, whether that be expectant management, intrauterine fetal Laser therapy, intrauterine transfusion (IUT), selective reduction (SR) or early delivery, is currently unknown¹². Perinatal outcome may range in severity from an isolated but significant difference in hemoglobin levels at birth to intrauterine demise, neonatal death or severe neonatal morbidity^{13, 14}. Moreover, TAPS is associated with cerebral injury and neurodevelopmental impairment¹⁵⁻¹⁸. However, it is also possible that the associated perinatal mortality and morbidity are related to prematurity.

The aim of this systematic review was to report the perinatal outcome of MCDA twin pregnancy complicated by TAPS, according to the type of disease (spontaneous or post-laser) and the management option adopted.

METHODS

Eligibility criteria, information sources and search strategy

This review was performed according to an a priori designed protocol recommended for systematic reviews and meta-analyses¹⁹. Medline, Embase and Cochrane Library databases were searched electronically in May 2020, utilizing combinations of the relevant medical subject heading (MeSH) terms, key words and word variants for “twin pregnancies” and “anemia polycythemia sequence” (Table S1). The search and selection criteria were restricted to the English language. Reference lists of relevant articles and reviews were searched manually for additional reports. PRISMA and MOOSE guidelines were followed²⁰⁻²². The study was registered with the PROSPERO database (Registration number: CRD42019157820).

Study selection

Inclusion criteria were non-anomalous MCDA twin pregnancies with either a prenatal diagnosis of TAPS, defined as MCA-PSV >1.5 MoM in one twin and <1 MoM in the second twin, with normal amniotic fluid volume, or a postnatal diagnosis of TAPS, defined as the presence of inter-twin hemoglobin difference ≥ 8.0 g/dL and at least one of the following: small residual anastomoses at the placental surface after color dye injection and/or reticulocyte count ratio (donor/recipient reticulocyte count) ≥ 1.7 ². Exclusion criteria were incomplete information on the type of TAPS or on pregnancy management, and inclusion of pregnancies with coexisting TAPS and TTTS.

The primary outcome was mortality, including overall, single and double intra-uterine death (IUD), neonatal death (NND), defined as the death up to 28 days of life, and perinatal death (PND), defined as IUD or NND, live-birth and survival of at least one twin or of both twins (up to 28 days).

The secondary outcomes were severe neurological morbidity, respiratory morbidity, necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC), retinopathy of prematurity (ROP), patent ductus arteriosus (PDA), severe neonatal morbidity, intact survival and preterm birth <37 , <34 , <32 and <28 weeks of gestation. Severe neurological morbidity included intraventricular hemorrhage stage ≥ 3 , ventricular dilatation, including post-hemorrhagic ventricular dilatation, cystic periventricular leukomalacia grade ≥ 2 , porencephalic or parenchymal cysts, arterial infarction and other severe cerebral lesions associated with adverse outcome. Respiratory morbidity included respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) requiring mechanical ventilation and surfactant, pulmonary hypertension and bronchopulmonary dysplasia. Severe neonatal morbidity included at least one of the following: RDS requiring mechanical ventilation and

surfactant, PDA requiring treatment, NEC stage ≥ 2 , ROP stage ≥ 3 , amniotic band syndrome, ischemic limb injury and severe neurological morbidity. Intact survival was defined as survival free from severe neurological complications. A sub-group analysis was performed considering spontaneous and iatrogenic PTB separately.

Outcomes were stratified according to the type of TAPS (spontaneous or following Laser treatment for TTTS) and according to the management option adopted (expectant, Laser, IUT or SR) only when TAPS was diagnosed prenatally.

Data extraction

Two authors (VG, AM) reviewed all abstracts independently. Agreement regarding potential relevance was reached by consensus; full text copies of those papers considered potentially eligible were obtained, and the same two reviewers independently extracted relevant data regarding study characteristics and pregnancy outcome. Consensus on inconsistencies was reached by discussion by the two reviewers or with a third author (FD). If more than one study was published on the same cohort with identical endpoints, the report containing the most comprehensive information on the population was included to avoid overlapping populations. Studies that reported on TAPS cases from the same centers as those included in the TAPS registry were excluded in order to avoid including overlapping data with the study of Tollenaar et al.²³. For studies in which information was not reported but the methodology was such that this information would have been recorded initially, the authors were contacted.

Assessment of risk of bias

Quality assessment of the included studies was performed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for cohort studies. According to NOS, each study is judged on three broad perspectives: selection of the study groups, comparability of the groups and ascertainment of the outcome of interest. Assessment of the selection of a study includes evaluation of the representativeness of the exposed cohort, selection of the non-exposed cohort, ascertainment of the exposure and demonstration that the outcome of interest was not present at the start of the study. Assessment of the comparability of the study includes evaluation of the comparability of the cohorts based on the design or analysis. Assessment of ascertainment of the outcome of interest includes evaluation of the type of assessment of the outcome of interest and the length and adequacy of follow-up. According to NOS, a study can be awarded a maximum of one star for each numbered item within the Selection and Outcome categories. A maximum of two stars can be given for Comparability²⁴.

For case reports and case series, quality of the included studies was assessed using the evaluation tool for methodological quality and synthesis of case series and case reports described by Murad et al.²⁵. According to this tool, each study is judged on four broad perspectives: selection of the study groups, ascertainment and causality of the outcome observed, and reporting of the case.

Statistical Analysis

Random-effects meta-analyses of proportions were used to analyze the data. Between study heterogeneity was explored using the I^2 statistic, which represents the percentage of between-study variation that is due to heterogeneity rather than chance. A value of 0% indicates that no heterogeneity is observed, while values >50% are associated with substantial heterogeneity. A random effects model was ultimately used for all meta-analyses because of the heterogeneity identified between studies. Publication bias was assessed with an exploratory aim, using Egger's test as well as funnel plots for visual inspection. Tests for funnel plot asymmetry were not used when the total number of publications included for each outcome was less than ten, as the tests lack power to detect real asymmetry in these instances. StatsDirect 3.0.171 (StatsDirect Ltd, Altrincham) and RevMan 5.3 (The Nordic Cochrane Centre, The Cochrane Collaboration, 2014) statistical software was used to analyse the data.

RESULTS

General characteristics

The search identified 265 articles, of which 122 were assessed with respect to their eligibility for inclusion and 40 were included in the systematic review^{8, 16, 23, 26-62} (Table 1, Figure S1). 38 studies reported outcome according to the type of TAPS in 502 pregnancies (306 (61.0%) with spontaneous TAPS and 196 (39.0%) with post-Laser TAPS) and 21 studies reported outcome according to management in 417 pregnancies with TAPS diagnosed prenatally. In the latter group, 177 (42.4%) pregnancies were managed expectantly, 120 (28.8%) were treated by Laser, 86 (20.6%) were treated by IUT and 34 (8.2%) were treated by SR. The rates of spontaneous and post-Laser TAPS were 58% and 42% in the expectant management group, 76% and 24% in the laser group, 34% and 66% in the IUT group and 53% and 47% in the SR group, respectively.

The results of the quality assessment of the included studies using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) are presented in Table S2. Most of the included studies showed an overall acceptable score regarding selection and comparability of the study groups, as well as for ascertainment of the outcome of interest and reporting of the case. The main weaknesses of the studies were their retrospective design, small sample size and heterogeneity in timing of diagnosis and in prenatal management of TAPS.

Synthesis of results

Mortality

Spontaneous vs post-Laser TAPS

IUD occurred in 5.2% (28/612, 95% CI, 3.6–7.1) of fetuses with spontaneous TAPS and in 10.2% (37/392, 95% CI, 7.4-13.3) of those with post-Laser TAPS, while the corresponding rates of NND were 4.0% (19/610, 95% CI, 2.6-5.7) and 9.2% (35/392, 95% CI, 6.6-12.3), respectively. The rate of PND was 8.3% (47/612, 95% CI, 6.3-10.6) among fetuses with spontaneous TAPS and 19.0% (72/392, 95% CI, 11.7-27.6) among those with post-Laser TAPS (Table 2, Figure 1a).

In the sub-group of twins affected by spontaneous TAPS, the livebirth rate was 90.5% (554/612), while the corresponding rate for fetuses affected by post-Laser TAPS was 84.1% (330/392, 95% CI, 80.0-87.2).

Comparison of different management options

IUD occurred in 9.8% (28/354, 95% CI, 4.3-17.1) of fetuses managed expectantly and in 13.1% (30/240, 95% CI, 9.2-17.6), 12.1% (19/172, 95% CI, 7.7-17.3) and 7.6% (2/34, 95% CI, 1.3-18.5) of those treated with Laser, IUT and SR, respectively (Table 3, Figure 2a). There were no cases of double IUD in the group of pregnancies treated with Laser surgery

or IUT, while 8.5% (2/42, 95% CI, 2.3-17.9) of pregnancies managed expectantly experienced double IUD.

The livebirth rate was 92.1% (326/354), 87.5% (210/240), 88.9% (153/172) and 94.1% (32/34) in the expectant management, Laser surgery, IUT and SR groups, respectively.

Morbidity

Spontaneous vs post-Laser TAPS

Severe neonatal morbidity occurred in 29.3% (162/546, 95% CI, 25.6-33.1) of twins after spontaneous TAPS and in 33.3% (117/309, 95% CI, 17.4-51.8) after post-Laser TAPS (Table S3, Figure 1b). Severe neurological morbidity affected 4.0% (17/546, 95% CI, 3.5-5.7) of twins with spontaneous TAPS compared to 11.1% (33/309, 95% CI, 6.2-17.2) of those with post-Laser TAPS, while respiratory morbidity affected 24.8% (136/546, 95% CI, 21.3-28.5) of twins with spontaneous TAPS and 23.8% (95% CI, 9.1-42.8) of those with post-Laser TAPS. The rates of NEC, PDA and ROP were similar for the two types of TAPS. Survival without neurological impairment was observed in 96.0% (529/546, 95% CI, 94.3-97.5) of twins after spontaneous TAPS and in 80.2% (276/309, 95% CI, 64.5-92.2) of those after post-Laser TAPS.

Comparison of different management options

Severe neonatal morbidity affected 27.3% (71/296, 95% CI, 13.6-43.6) of twins in the expectant management group, 28.7% (57/198, 95% CI, 22.7-35.1) of those in the Laser surgery group, 38.2% (64/151, 95% CI 18.3-60.5) of those in the IUT group and 23.3% (7/31, 95% CI 10.5-39.2) of those in the SR group (Table S4, Figure 2b).

Severe neurological morbidity was observed in 7.8% (22/296, 95% CI, 5.1-11.1) of twins managed expectantly, in 4.0% (6/168, 95% CI, 1.7-7.1) of those after Laser treatment and in 9.8% (14/151, 95% CI, 5.7-15.0) of those after receiving IUT. The rate of survival without neurological complications was 92.2% (274/296, 95% CI 88.9-94.9) in twins managed expectantly, while the corresponding rates for those treated with Laser, IUT and SR were 95.5% (190/198, 95% CI 92.3-97.9), 81.7%, (134/151, 95% CI 60.9-95.7) and 100% (31/31, 95% CI 91.1-100.0), respectively.

Preterm birth

Spontaneous vs post-Laser TAPS

The overall rate of PTB in pregnancies complicated by spontaneous TAPS was 86.3% (51/57, 95% CI, 77.2- 93.3), with 59.8% (28/46, 95% CI, 47.0-72.0) delivered <34 weeks, 30.2% (12/46, 95% CI, 18.0-44.0) delivered <32 weeks and none delivered <28 weeks, respectively (Table S5, Figure 1c). All cases of post-Laser TAPS delivered preterm, with

79.5% (27/33, 95% CI, 65.6-90.5) delivered <34 weeks, 58.8% (20/33, 95% CI, 39.9-76.4) delivered <32 weeks and 21.8% (6/33, 95% CI, 10.4-35.9) delivered <28 weeks. Iatrogenic PTB was more frequent than spontaneous PTB in both groups (spontaneous TAPS: 61.3%, 95% CI, 42.1-78.8 vs 32.3%, 95% CI, 17.1-49.8; post-Laser TAPS: 79.4%, 95% CI, 58.9-94.1 vs 20.6%, 95% CI, 5.9-41.1).

Comparison of different management options

Overall, PTB complicated 80.4% (16/20, 95% CI, 59.8-94.8), 73.4% (8/10, 95% CI, 48.1-92.3), 100% (16/16, 95% CI, 76.5-100) and 100% (4/4, 95% CI, 39.8-100) of pregnancies after expectant management, Laser, IUT and SR, respectively (Table S6, Figure 2c). The rate of PTB <34 weeks was 68.3% (14/20, 95% CI, 49.0-84.9) in the expectant management group, 50.9% (5/10, 95% CI, 25.8-75.8) in the Laser group, 81.1% (14/16, 95% CI, 61.5-94.8) in the IUT group and 75.0% (3/4, 95% CI, 19.4-99.4) in the SR group. The rates of PTB <32 and <28 weeks in the IUT group were 76.2% (13/16, 95% CI, 55.7-91.8) and 19.9% (2/16, 95% CI, 3.7-44.7), respectively, which were higher than those in the expectant management and Laser groups. Whereas iatrogenic PTB was more frequent than spontaneous PTB in the expectant management group (82.5%, 95% CI, 61.8-96.2 vs 17.5%, 95% CI, 3.8-38.2) and the IUT group (100%, 95% CI, 58.1-100 vs 27.3%, 95% CI, 18.0-37.6), an opposite trend was observed in the Laser group (30.3%, 95% CI, 8.4-59.3 vs 56.0%, 95% CI, 47.0-64.9).

DISCUSSION

Summary of main findings

The findings from this systematic review suggest that the risks of perinatal mortality and severe neurological morbidity are relatively higher in twin pregnancies complicated by post-Laser compared to spontaneous TAPS, although a direct comparison could not be performed in view of the design of the included studies. PND occurred in 8.3% of cases after spontaneous TAPS and in 19.0% after post-Laser TAPS. Likewise, the rate of severe neurological morbidity was higher after post-Laser TAPS (11.1%) compared to spontaneous TAPS (4.0%). The small number of included cases when considering the different management options did not allow objective evidence on the optimal type of management for TAPS to be extrapolated.

Comparison with existing literature, strengths and limitations

This is, to date, the largest meta-analysis reporting the rates of perinatal mortality and morbidity in pregnancies complicated by TAPS, according to the type of TAPS and the management option adopted. Nevertheless, the small size of the included studies, their retrospective design and the heterogeneity in management are the main limitations of this review. In particular, it was not possible to stratify the results within each management group according to the type of TAPS.

While the overall rate of neonatal mortality in TAPS is similar to that in uncomplicated monochorionic twin pregnancies⁶³, differences in the rates of perinatal mortality between post-Laser and spontaneous TAPS have yet to be established^{23, 26, 27, 38, 42, 51, 64}. In a previous review by Rossi and Prefumo, the overall survival rate was 86% in 17 pregnancies with spontaneous TAPS and 79% in 11 cases with TAPS after Laser for TTTS, but the difference was not significant⁶⁵. However, the post-laser group was treated in utero more frequently and required postnatal procedures less frequently than the spontaneous group⁶⁵. It was not possible to stratify the analysis according to ultrasound staging of the disease, and data on long-term outcome were reported in only a small minority of included cases, thus not allowing a comprehensive estimation of the risk of long-term sequelae after TAPS. The recent results of a large international registry showed high rates of perinatal mortality and severe neonatal morbidity in spontaneous TAPS, post-Laser TAPS and in each TAPS management group (expectant management, Laser surgery, IUT, delivery and SR), highlighting the substantial heterogeneity both of the condition and of its management, as undertaken by 17 fetal therapy centers^{23, 26, 27}.

Approximately 10% of neonates born after post-Laser TAPS experience severe adverse neurological outcome^{27, 38, 44, 66}. Slaghekke and colleagues reported that, after post-laser TAPS, long-term neurodevelopmental impairment (NDI) is frequent (9%), and the rate was similar in donors compared with recipients; however, the rate was not higher than that in survivors who did not develop TAPS after Laser¹⁸. Twins born after a diagnosis of spontaneous TAPS can also experience severe neurological pathology, but apparently less frequently than those born after post-Laser TAPS^{15, 16, 26, 42, 67}. Tollenaar et al. evaluated long-term NDI in spontaneous TAPS survivors and reported that it occurs in 31% of cases and is more frequent in donors than in recipients¹⁷. Similarly, only donors showed bilateral deafness (15%). The authors identified gestational age at birth and severe anemia as being risk factors for neurodevelopment impairment. As the small sample size and variety of tests used for neurodevelopment evaluation limit the interpretation of these data, larger studies are necessary to investigate the long-term neurodevelopment of twins after TAPS¹⁷.

The results of the present systematic review demonstrate that both spontaneous and post-laser TAPS present an increased risk of iatrogenic preterm delivery; in particular, pregnancies affected by post-Laser TAPS exhibited more severe prematurity. This might be due to post-laser TAPS being diagnosed prenatally more frequently than spontaneous TAPS, leading to more frequent surveillance and intervention in monochorionic twin pregnancies undergoing Laser for TTTS. Conversely, cases with spontaneous TAPS that are diagnosed postnatally are likely to be treated prenatally as being “uncomplicated” MCDA pregnancies and therefore induced later in pregnancy. Moreover, it is well-known that Laser surgery itself increases the risk of prematurity in monochorionic twin pregnancy^{68, 69}.

A recent systematic review of 105 cases of TAPS that underwent different intrauterine interventions showed no differences in the rates of mortality and morbidity between expectant management, Laser therapy and IUT¹². However, the rate of adverse perinatal outcome was found to be significantly lower in Laser-treated and IUT-managed TAPS cases when compared to expectantly managed TAPS cases. Similarly, comparable results were found for severe neonatal morbidity between the different management options in a large international study²³. However, the authors showed that the prevalence of postnatal TAPS and the risk of need for hematological treatment were significantly lower in the Laser group than in the other management groups, and, thus, they speculated a key role of laser therapy in the treatment of TAPS²³. Although our findings should be interpreted with caution in view of the limitations of the included studies, they did not demonstrate marked differences in terms of mortality and morbidity according to the different management options for TAPS.

Clinical and research implications

Knowledge of the natural history of spontaneous and post-laser TAPS could be useful for providing accurate prenatal counselling, defining appropriate monitoring and guiding the optimal individualized management. Firstly, the high perinatal mortality associated with post-Laser TAPS should be considered carefully during prenatal counselling. Moreover, such high perinatal mortality must be counteracted by strict ultrasound monitoring of these complicated pregnancies, particularly if TAPS develops after intrauterine Laser surgery for TTTS. This is consistent with the recent update of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidance on twin and multiple pregnancies, which recommends that twin pregnancies complicated by TTTS and treated by Laser surgery should have ultrasound monitoring for the development of TAPS using MCA PSV and other ultrasound findings^{70, 71}. While a stable and chronic clinical condition of the anemic and polycythemic twins can be managed conservatively, any sudden worsening of fetal hemodynamic or cardiac impairment should trigger active prenatal fetal intervention. The exact nature of this fetal intervention will vary according to gestational age, the severity of TAPS and the presence of co-existing TTTS and/or fetal growth restriction. The proportions of twins with co-existing severe or moderate fetal growth restriction account for 23% and 44%, respectively, of cases of post-Laser TAPS, with similar risks in the donors and recipients²⁷. In spontaneous TAPS, on the other hand, 29% and 49%, respectively, of cases are reported to have coexisting severe or moderate fetal growth restriction, with a significant predominance in donors²⁶. This could be due to the fact that spontaneous TAPS may be a chronic and enduring condition in which the roles of the donor and recipient do not change throughout the pregnancy, while, in post-laser TAPS, the donor is less likely to become growth restricted because they are often former TTTS recipients, which are usually larger than TTTS donors⁸.

The reluctance to adopt routine antenatal monitoring for TAPS, as evidenced in the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) and NICE guidelines^{70, 72}, could be explained by the scarce data on the natural history of TAPS, validation of the antenatal diagnostic criteria, perinatal outcome and the optimal management strategy. Over the last few years, researchers have been aiming to address some of these uncertainties, including a Delphi consensus on the antenatal diagnostic criteria for TAPS⁷³, a validation study of these criteria⁷⁴ and a multicenter international registry reporting on the perinatal outcome of twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS according to the onset, severity and management options^{23, 26, 27}.

Conclusions

The rates of perinatal mortality and morbidity are relatively higher in post-Laser compared to spontaneous TAPS, although a direct comparison between these two entities could not be performed. The findings from the systematic review highlight the need of appropriately designed and powered randomized controlled trials aimed at evaluating the impact of different management options on perinatal mortality and morbidity in twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS.

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Figure legend

Figure 1. Forest plots of the pooled proportions of perinatal mortality (a), neonatal morbidity (b) and preterm birth (c) in monochorionic diamniotic twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS, according to whether TAPS occurred spontaneously or post-laser.

Figure 2. Forest plots of the pooled proportions of perinatal mortality (a), neonatal morbidity (b) and preterm birth (c) in monochorionic diamniotic twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS, according to the different management approaches. PND perinatal death, IUT intra-uterine transfusion, SR selective reduction.

Figure S1 PRISMA flow diagram summarizing inclusion of studies in the systematic review

Table 1 General characteristics of the studies included in the systematic review, reporting on the perinatal outcome of twin anemia–polycythemia sequence

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Period considered	Type of TAPS	Outcomes observed	Pregnancies (n)	TAPS (n)
Tollenaar et al. ²³	2020	Multinational*	Retro register-based cohort	2014-2019	spontaneous, post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	370	370
Tollenaar et al. ²⁶	2020	Multinational*	Retro register-based cohort	2014-2019	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	249	249
Tollenaar et al. ²⁷	2020	Multinational*	Retro register-based cohort	2014-2019	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	173	173
Murata et al. ²⁸	2020	Japan	Retro cohort	2010-2015	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	90	1
Han et al. ²⁹	2020	Korea	Retro cohort	2003-2006	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	172	11
Suzuki et al. ³⁰	2019	Japan	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality	1	1
Perez et al. ³¹	2018	Poland	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Sheales et al. ³²	2017	Australia	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Robinson et al. ³³	2017	Australia	Retro cohort	2007-2016	spontaneous	mortality	33	2
Gosavi et al. ³⁴	2017	Singapore	Cohort study	2015	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	8	1
Brinsmead et al. ³⁵	2017	Australia	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality	1	1
Takeuchi et al. ³⁶	2016	Japan	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Suzuki ³⁷	2016	Japan	Retro cohort	2011-2014	spontaneous	mortality	88	2
Moaddab et al. ³⁸	2016	USA	Case series	NR	spontaneous, post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	2	2
Guenot et al. ³⁹	2016	Switzerland	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Dassios et al. ⁴⁰	2016	UK	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Bae et al. ⁴¹	2016	Korea	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Ashwal et al. ⁴²	2015	Israel	Retro cohort	2011-2014	spontaneous, post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	179	10
Yokouchi et al. ⁴³	2015	Japan	Prosp cohort	2006-2013	spontaneous	mortality	185	3
Taniguchi et al. ⁴⁴	2015	Japan	Case series	2003-2012	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	3	3
Abdel-Sattar et al. ⁴⁵	2015	USA	Case series	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	3	3
Yarci et al. ⁴⁶	2014	Turkey	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Stritzke et al. ⁴⁷	2014	Canada	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Soundararajan et al. ⁴⁸	2014	UK	Case series	NR	spontaneous, post-Laser	mortality	2	2
Sainz et al. ⁴⁹	2014	Spain	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Movva et al. ⁵⁰	2014	USA	Case series	NR	spontaneous	mortality	2	2
Mabuchi et al. ⁵¹	2014	Japan	Retro cohort	2003-2012	spontaneous, post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	432	7
Ishii et al. ⁵²	2014	Japan	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Casanova et al. ⁵³	2014	Portugal	Case series	NR	spontaneous	mortality	3	3
Ruano et al. ⁵⁴	2013	Brazil, Spain, USA	Retro cohort	2010-2012	post-Laser	mortality	102	6
Luminoso et al. ¹⁶	2013	Brazil	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Groussolles et al. ⁵⁵	2012	France	Case report	NR	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Fratelli et al. ⁵⁶	2012	Italy	Case report	NR	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Biran et al. ⁵⁷	2011	France	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Weingertner et al. ⁵⁸	2010	France	Case series	2006-2008	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	4	4
Chmait et al. ⁵⁹	2010	USA	Prosp cohort	2006-2009	post-Laser	mortality	105	1
Herway et al. ⁶⁰	2009	USA	Case report	NR	post-Laser	mortality, morbidity	1	1
de Laat et al. ⁶¹	2009	Netherlands	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality	1	1
Sunagawa et al. ⁶²	2008	Japan	Case report	NR	spontaneous	mortality, morbidity	1	1
Robyr et al. ⁸	2006	France, Belgium	Prosp cohort study	Until 2004	post-Laser	mortality	151	13

*Netherlands, Belgium, Spain, Germany, France, Austria, Canada, Italy USA, UK, Australia, Sweden and Russia. Prosp, prospective, Retro, retrospective.

Table 2 Pooled proportions of mortality in monochorionic diamniotic twin pregnancies complicated by TAPS, according to whether TAPS was spontaneous or post-Laser

Outcome	Studies (n)	Fetuses (n/N)	I ²	Pooled proportions (95% CI)
Spontaneous TAPS				
Intrauterine demise (overall)	27	28/612	0	5.18 (3.6-7.1)
Single intrauterine demise	26	2/118	0	5.26 (2.2-9.7)
Double intrauterine demise	26	1/118	0	4.45 (1.6-8.6)
Neonatal death (overall)	26	19/610	0	4.00 (2.6-5.7)
Single neonatal death	25	1/116	0	5.09 (2.0-9.5)
Double neonatal death	25	0/116	0	0 (0-8.1)
Perinatal death (overall)	27	47/612	0	8.33 (6.3-10.6)
Single perinatal death	26	3/118	0	6.47 (2.9-11.3)
Double perinatal death	26	1/118	0	4.45 (1.6-8.6)
Livebirths	27	554/612	0	90.12 (87.7-92.3)
Survival of at least one twin	26	61/118	0	52.02 (43.2-60.5)
Survival of both twins	26	58/118	0	49.15 (40.6-57.7)
Post-Laser TAPS				
Intrauterine demise (overall)	14	37/392	0	10.15 (7.4-13.3)
Single intrauterine demise	13	2/64	0	6.93 (2.2-14.0)
Double intrauterine demise	13	1/64	0	5.15 (1.3-11.5)
Neonatal death (overall)	14	35/392	23.5	9.24 (6.6-12.3)
Single neonatal death	13	2/64	0	7.46 (2.5-14.7)
Double neonatal death	13	3/64	0	7.00 (2.3-14.1)
Perinatal death (overall)	14	72/392	19.7	19.01 (11.7-27.6)
Single perinatal death	13	4/64	0	10.08 (4.2-18.1)
Double perinatal death	13	4/64	0	8.03 (2.9-15.4)
Livebirths	14	330/392	0	83.70 (80.0-87.2)
Survival of at least one twin	13	29/64	0	45.57 (34.2-57.2)
Survival of both twins	13	23/64	0	37.16 (23.6-48.7)

Table 3 Pooled proportions of mortality in monochorionic diamniotic twin pregnancies complicated by spontaneous or post-Laser TAPS, according to different management options

Outcome	Studies (n)	Fetuses (n/N)	I ²	Pooled proportions (95% CI)
Expectant management				
Intrauterine demise (overall)	12	28/354	15.2	9.76 (4.3-17.1)
Single intrauterine demise	11	0/42	0	0 (0-13.0)
Double intrauterine demise	11	2/42	0	8.46 (2.3-17.9)
Neonatal death (overall)	11	27/352	0	8.05 (5.5-11.1)
Single neonatal death	10	1/40	0	7.01 (1.5-16.2)
Double neonatal death	10	1/40	0	7.01 (1.5-16.2)
Perinatal death (overall)	12	55/354	46.5	15.81 (6.2-28.8)
Single perinatal death	11	1/42	0	7.12 (1.6-16.1)
Double perinatal death	11	3/42	0	9.89 (3.1-19.9)
Livebirth	12	326/354	0.4	92.23 (89.1-94.9)
Survival of at least one twin	12	168/354	0	47.46 (42.3-52.6)
Survival of both twins	12	133/354	0	37.74 (32.8-42.8)
Laser therapy				
Intrauterine demise (overall)	9	30/240	0	13.13 (9.2-17.6)
Single intrauterine demise	8	2/20	0	15.38 (4.1-32.2)
Double intrauterine demise	8	0/20	0	0 (0-21.1)
Neonatal death (overall)	9	10/240	0	4.99 (2.6-8.1)
Single neonatal death	8	0/20	0	0 (0-21.1)
Double neonatal death	8	0/20	0	0 (0-21.1)
Perinatal death (overall)	9	40/240	0	17.22 (12.8-22.2)
Single perinatal death	8	2/20	0	15.38 (4.1-32.2)
Double perinatal death	8	0/20	0	0 (0-21.1)
Livebirth	9	210/240	0	86.87 (82.4-90.8)
Survival of at least one twin	9	109/240	0	45.51 (39.3-51.8)
Survival of both twins	9	86/240	0	36.06 (30.2-42.2)
Intra-uterine transfusion				
Intrauterine demise (overall)	9	19/172	0	12.08 (7.7-17.3)
Single intrauterine demise	8	1/32	0	8.37 (1.7-19.5)
Double intrauterine demise	8	0/32	0	0 (0-13.5)
Neonatal death (overall)	9	9/172	31.2	7.93 (1.7-18.1)
Single neonatal death	8	0/32	0	0 (0-13.5)
Double neonatal death	8	1/32	0	5.95 (0.7-15.9)
Perinatal death (overall)	9	28/172	16.4	15.51 (7.6-25.6)
Single perinatal death	8	1/32	0	8.37 (1.7-19.5)
Double perinatal death	8	1/32	0	5.95 (0.7-15.9)

Livebirth	9	153/172	0	87.92 (82.7-92.3)
Survival of at least one twin	9	82/172	0	47.63 (40.3-55.0)
Survival of both twins	9	63/172	0	36.89 (29.9-44.1)
	Selective reduction			
Intrauterine demise	2	2/34	0	7.61 (1.3-18.5)
Neonatal death	2	1/34	0	2.31 (0.1-9.8)
Perinatal death	2	3/34	0	11.63 (1.4-30.0)
Livebirths	2	32/34	0	92.39 (81.5-98.1)
Survival of at least one twin	2	31/34	0	88.37 (70.0-98.6)